

Third order Semi-Canonical Quasi-linear Differential Equations with Mixed Arguments: Oscillation via Canonical Transform

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Abstract. In this paper, we present some results on the oscillatory behavior of solutions of the third-order nonlinear unstable type semi-canonical quasi-linear differential equation with mixed arguments of the form

$$(r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' - q_1(l)Z^\beta(\sigma(l))q_2(l)Z^\gamma(\tau(l)), \quad l \geq l_0$$

(E)

Oscillation conditions are obtained by converting the semi-canonical equation into canonical type and then applying comparison method and integral averaging technique. Examples are provided to validate our main results.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we consider the oscillatory behavior of solutions of the third order nonlinear unstable type semi-canonical quasi-linear differential equations of the form

$$(r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' - q_1(l)Z^\beta(\sigma(l)) - q_2(l)Z^\gamma(\tau(l)), \quad l \geq l_0$$

(E)

where the following conditions are always assumed to hold:

(H1): α, β and γ are the ratio of odd positive integers;

(H2): $r_1(l), r_2(l), q_1(l), q_2(l) \in C([l_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$;

(H3): $\sigma(l)$ and $\tau(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathbb{R})$, $\sigma(l) > l$, $\tau(l) < l$, $\tau'(l) \geq 0$, $\sigma'(l) \geq 0$

and $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \tau(l) = \infty$, for all $l \geq l_0$

(H4): The equation (E) is in semi-canonical form:

$$\mathcal{A}_2(l_0) = \int_{l_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_2(s)} ds < \infty \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{l_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_1(s)} ds = \infty \quad (1.1)$$

By a solution of (E), we understand a function $Z(l) \in C([T_Z, \infty))$, $T_Z \geq l_0$, $r_1(l)Z'(l)^\alpha$, $(r_2(l)(r_1(l)Z'(l))^\alpha)'$ are continuously differentiable and satisfy equation (E) on $([T_Z, \infty))$. We consider only those solutions $Z(l)$ of (E) which satisfy $\sup\{|Z(l)| : l \geq T\} > 0$ for all $T \geq T_Z$. Such a solution of equation (E) is called oscillatory if it has arbitrarily large zeros on $[T_Z, \infty)$ otherwise it is called nonoscillatory.

In [1,4,17], the authors discussed the oscillation of all solutions of the third-order nonlinear functional differential equation of the form

$$(a(t)(x''(t))^\gamma)' = q(t)f(x(g(t))) + p(t)h(x(\sigma(t)))$$

with $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(s)} ds = \infty$ or $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(s)} ds < \infty$.

In [28], oscillatory solutions of third order quasi-linear delay differential equation

$$(p_2(t)(p_1(t)(y'(t))^\alpha)')' + f(t)y^\beta(\tau(t)) = 0$$

With $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b(s)} ds < \infty$ or $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(s)} ds = \infty$ is studied by transforming the semi-canonical equation into the canonical form.

Following this trend, our objective in this paper is to establish criteria for all solutions of equation (E) to be oscillatory. The criteria will be developed by transforming the equation (E) into the canonical form. Consequently our results are new and extended the earlier ones in [1,11,16,17,26,29]. Examples are presented to illustrate the importance and novelty of the main results.

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The following notations are used to simplify our main results:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_2(l) &= \int_l^\infty \frac{1}{r_2(s)} ds & r_2^*(l) &= r_2(l)\mathcal{A}_2^2(l) & r_1^*(l) &= \frac{r_1(l)}{\mathcal{A}_2(l)} \\ \mathcal{Q}_1(l) &= \mathcal{A}_2(l)q_1(l) & \mathcal{Q}_2(l) &= \mathcal{A}_2(l)q_2(l) & H_1(l) &= \int_{\delta(l)}^{\sigma(l)} \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{1/\alpha}} du \\ H_2(l) &= \mathcal{Q}_1(l)H_1^\beta(l) & H_3(l) &= H_2(l) \left(\int_{\omega(l)}^{\delta(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \right)^{\beta/\alpha}, & G_1(l) &= \mathcal{Q}_2(l) \int_{l_1}^{\tau(l)} \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{1/\alpha}} du \\ G_2(l) &= G_1(l) \left(\int_{\tau(l)}^{\varsigma(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \right)^{\gamma/\alpha} & U_1(l) &= (\mathcal{Q}_1(l) + \mathcal{Q}_2(l)) \int_{l_1}^{\tau(l)} \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{1/\alpha}} du \\ U_2(l) &= U_1(l) \left(\int_{\tau(l)}^{\varsigma(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \right)^{\gamma/\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

where $l_1 \geq l_0$ is sufficiently large.

Next, we derive canonical form of equation (E) when (1.1) holds. To start with, let us state a characterization of possible nonoscillatory solutions of (E) when (1.1) holds.

Lemma 2.1. Assume that $Z(l)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E) then there exists a $l_1 \geq l_0$ such that for $l_1 \geq l_0$ for $l \geq l_1$, the function satisfies one of the following three possibilities:

$$\begin{aligned} (C_0): & Z(l) > 0, Z'(l) < 0, (r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' > 0, (r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq 0 \\ (C_1): & Z(l) > 0, Z'(l) > 0, (r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' > 0, (r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq 0 \\ (C_2): & Z(l) > 0, Z'(l) > 0, (r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' < 0, (r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

The above lemma can be found in [29]. Further, the set of nonoscillatory solutions of (E) satisfies three types when case (1.1) holds. To find the oscillation criteria for the equation (E), hence we eliminate these three types of nonoscillatory solutions. In the following using a simple condition, we transform the equation (E) into canonical form, which reduces the classes of three possible cases into two. So this simplifies our investigation to find criteria for the oscillation of all solutions of (E).

Theorem 2.2. If

$$\int_{l_0}^\infty \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}_2(s)}{r_1(s)} \right)^{1/\alpha} ds = \infty \quad (2.1)$$

then the semi-canonical operator has the canonical form

$$(r_2(l)(r_1(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' = \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}_2(l)} (r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \quad (2.2)$$

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 2.2 in [15] and so the details are omitted.

Now from Theorem 2.2, the equation (E) can be written in the canonical form as

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{A}_2(l)} (r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' = q_1(l)Z^\beta(\sigma(l)) + q_2(l)Z^\gamma(\tau(l))$$

or

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' = Q_1(l)Z^\beta(\sigma(l)) + Q_2(l)Z^\gamma(\tau(l)) \quad (E_1)$$

where $r_2^*(l) = r_2(l)\mathcal{A}_2^2(l)$ and $r_1^*(l) = \frac{r_1(l)}{\mathcal{A}_2(l)}$.

Remark 2.3. In [15], by Corollary 2.3 and 2.4, the semi-canonical equation (E) possess a positive solution $Z(l)$ if and only if the canonical equation (E₁) also has a positive solution $Z(l)$.

From the above remark, it is clear that the investigation of the oscillation of (E) is reduced to that of (E₁) and therefore, if $Z(l)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E₁) then the function satisfies $Z(l)$ one of the following two cases:

$$\begin{aligned} (C_1^*): Z(l) > 0, Z'(l) > 0, (r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' > 0, (r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' > 0 \\ (C_2^*): Z(l) > 0, Z'(l) > 0, (r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' < 0, (r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' > 0 \end{aligned}$$

3. OSCILLATION OF EQUATION (E)

In this section, we present oscillation criteria of (E) using the equation (E₁) and comparison with first-order functional differential equations. We begin with the following theorem:

Theorem 3.1. Let condition 2.1 holds. Assume that there exist non decreasing functions $\zeta(l), \delta(l), \omega(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that $\tau(l) < \zeta(l) < l$ and $\sigma(l) > \delta(l) > \omega(l) > l$ for $l \geq l_0$. If the advanced first-order differential equation

$$y'(l) - H_3(l)y^\beta(\omega(l)) = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

and the first-order delay differential equation

$$\eta'(l) + G_2(l)\eta^\gamma(\zeta(l)) = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

are oscillatory, then the equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Assume on the contrary that $Z(l)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E). Then by Remark 2.3, the corresponding function $Z(l)$ is also positive solution of (E₁) and hence $Z \in (C_1^*)$ or (C_2^*) for $l \geq l_1 \geq l_0$. Choose $l \geq l_1 \geq l_0$ so that $Z(l) > 0, Z(\tau(l)) > 0, Z(\sigma(l)) > 0$, for $l \geq l_1$.

First, assume that $Z \in (C_1^*)$: For $l \geq s \geq l_1$, we have

$$Z(l) - Z(s) = \int_s^l \frac{(r_1^*(u)(Z'(u))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du,$$

hence

$$Z(l) \geq (r_1^*(s)(Z'(s))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \int_s^l \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du \quad (3.3)$$

Replacing t and s in (3.3) by $\sigma(l)$ and $\delta(l)$ respectively, we get

$$Z(\sigma(l)) \geq H_1(l)(r_1^*(\delta(l))(Z'(\delta(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \text{ for } l \geq l_2 \geq l_1 \quad (3.4)$$

Substituting (3.4) in (E₁), we get

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq Q_1(l)H_1^\beta(l)(r_1^*(\delta(l))(Z'(\delta(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}} \quad (3.5)$$

Let $x(l) = r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha$, then (3.5) becomes

$$(r_2^*(l)x'(l))' \geq H_2(l)x^\beta(\delta(l)) \text{ for } l \geq l_2 \quad (3.6)$$

Once again for $l \geq s \geq l_2$, we have

$$x(l) - x(s) = \int_s^l \frac{r_2^*(u)x'(u)}{r_2^*(u)} du$$

and hence we have

$$x(l) \geq r_2^*(s)x'(s) \int_s^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \quad (3.7)$$

Replacing t and s by $\delta(l)$ and $\omega(l)$, respectively, we get

$$x(\delta(l)) \geq r_2^*(\omega(l))x'(\omega(l)) \int_{\omega(l)}^{\delta(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \text{ for } l \geq l_3 \geq l_2. \quad (3.8)$$

Let $y(l) = r_2^*(l)x'(l)$. Using (3.8) in (3.6) yields

$$y'(l) - H_3(l)y^{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}}(\omega(l)) \geq 0 \quad (3.9)$$

In view of Lemma 1 in [1], it follows that the corresponding differential equation (3.1) also has a positive solution, which is a contradiction.

Next, assume that $Z \in (C_2^*)$: For $l_1 \geq l_0$, we see that

$$Z(l) \geq (r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \int_{l_1}^l \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du$$

and hence

$$Z(\tau(l)) \geq (r_1^*(\tau(l))(Z'(\tau(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \int_{l_1}^{\tau(l)} \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du \quad (3.10)$$

Using the last inequality in equation (E₁), we have

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq G_1(l)(r_1^*(\tau(l))(Z'(\tau(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}} \quad (3.11)$$

Let $\xi(l) = r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha$ then

$$(r_2^*(l)\xi'(l))' \geq G_1(l)\xi^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\tau(l)). \quad (3.12)$$

Now for $l \geq s \geq l_1$, we have

$$\xi(s) - \xi(l) = \int_s^l \xi'(u) du$$

or

$$\xi(s) \geq - \int_s^l \frac{r_2^*(u)\xi'(u)}{r_2^*(u)} du \geq -r_2^*(l)\xi'(l) \int_s^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du$$

Replacing s and t by $\tau(l)$ and $\zeta(l)$, respectively, we have

$$\xi(\tau(l)) \geq -r_2^*(\zeta(l))\xi'(\zeta(l)) \int_{\tau(l)}^{\zeta(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \quad (3.13)$$

Letting $r_2^*(l)\xi'(l) = \eta(l)$ and using (3.12) in (3.11), we get

$$\eta'(l) + G_2(l)\eta^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\zeta(l)) \leq 0 \quad (3.14)$$

Integrating equation (3.13) from l to T and letting T tends to ∞ , we get

$$\eta(l) \geq \int_l^\infty G_2(s)\eta^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\zeta(s)) ds.$$

The function $\eta(l)$ is strictly decreasing on $[l_1, \infty)$ and therefore by Theorem 1 of [24], we observe that there exists a positive solution $\eta(l)$ of equation (3.2) such that $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \eta(l) = 0$ which is a contradiction. Hence equation (E₁) is oscillatory and by the oscillation preserving transformation, we conclude (E) that is also oscillatory. This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.2. Let condition 2.1 and $\beta = \gamma$ holds. Assume that there exist non decreasing functions $\zeta(l), \delta(l), \omega(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that $\tau(l) < \zeta(l) < l$ and $\sigma(l) > \delta(l) > \omega(l) > l$ for $l \geq l_0$. If the advanced first-order differential equation satisfies the same equation as (3.1) and the first-order delay differential equation

$$\kappa'(l) + U_2(l)\kappa^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\zeta(l)) = 0, \quad (3.15)$$

are oscillatory, then the equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Assume on the contrary that $Z(l)$ is an eventually positive solution of (E). Then by remark 2.3, the corresponding function $Z(l)$ is also positive solution of (E_1) and hence $Z \in (C_1^*)$ or (C_2^*) for $l \geq l_1 \geq l_0$. Choose $l \geq l_1 \geq l_0$ so that $Z(l) > 0, Z(\tau(l)) > 0, Z(\sigma(l)) > 0$, for $l \geq l_1$. For the case $Z \in (C_1^*)$ the proof is similar to that of Theorem 3.1.

If $\beta = \gamma$ and $Z(l)$ is a increasing function then $Z(\tau(l)) \leq Z(l) \leq Z(\sigma(l))$ then (E_1) becomes

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' = (Q_1(l) + Q_2(l))Z^\gamma(\tau(l))$$

Next, assume that $Z \in (C_2^*)$: For $l_1 \geq l_0$, we see that

$$Z(l) \geq (r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \int_{l_1}^l \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du$$

and hence

$$Z(\tau(l)) \geq (r_1^*(\tau(l))(Z'(\tau(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \int_{l_1}^{\tau(l)} \frac{1}{(r_1^*(u))^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} du$$

Using the last inequality in equation (E_1) , we have

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq U_1(l)(r_1^*(\tau(l))(Z'(\tau(l)))^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (3.16)$$

Let $\phi(l) = r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha$, then

$$(r_2^*(l)\phi'(l))' \geq U_1(l)\phi^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\tau(l)) \quad (3.17)$$

or

$$\phi(s) - \phi(l) = \int_s^l \phi'(u) du$$

or

$$\phi(s) \geq - \int_s^l \frac{r_2^*(u)\phi'(u)}{r_2^*(u)} du \geq -r_2^*(l)\phi'(l) \int_s^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du$$

Replacing s and t by $\tau(l)$ and $\zeta(l)$, respectively, we have

$$\phi(\tau(l)) \geq -r_2^*(\zeta(l))\phi'(\zeta(l)) \int_{\tau(l)}^{\zeta(l)} \frac{1}{r_2^*(u)} du \quad (3.18)$$

Letting $r_2^*(l)\phi'(l) = \kappa(l)$ and using (3.18) in (3.19). We get

$$\kappa'(l) + U_2(l)\kappa^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\zeta(l)) \leq 0, \quad (3.19)$$

Integrating equation (3.19) from l to T and letting T tends to ∞ , we get

$$\kappa(l) \geq \int_l^\infty U_2(s)\kappa^{\frac{\gamma}{\alpha}}(\zeta(s)) ds.$$

The function $\kappa(l)$ is strictly decreasing on $[l_1, \infty)$ and therefore by Theorem 1 of [21], we observe that there exist a positive solution $\kappa(l)$ of equation (3.2) such that $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \kappa(l) = 0$ which is a contradiction. Hence equation (E_1) is oscillatory and by the oscillation preserving transformation, we conclude that (E) is also oscillatory. This completes the proof.

Let condition (2.1) holds. Assume that there exist functions $\zeta(l), \delta(l), \omega(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that $\tau(l) < \zeta(l) < l$ and $\sigma(l) > \delta(l) > \omega(l) > l$ for $l \geq l_0$. In the following, we present explicit criteria for the oscillation of all solutions of (3.1), (3.2) and (3.15) which in turn implies the oscillation of (E).

Theorem 3.3. Let (2.1) holds. Assume that there exist nondecreasing function $\rho(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathfrak{R})$ such that

$$\rho(l) < l \text{ and } \mu(l) = \sigma(\rho(l)) > l \text{ for } l \geq l_0. \quad (3.20)$$

If the first-order advanced differential equations

$$\varpi'(l) - \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(l)} \int_{\rho(l)}^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s Q_1(u) \, duds \right)^{1/\alpha} \varpi^{\beta/\alpha}(\mu(l)) = 0 \quad (3.21)$$

and

$$\psi'(l) - \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(l)} \int_l^\infty \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_s^\infty Q_1(u) \, duds \right)^{1/\alpha} \psi^{\beta/\alpha}(\sigma(l)) = 0 \quad (3.22)$$

are oscillatory, then the equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. Assume the contrary that is an eventually positive solution $Z(l)$ of (E). Then proceeding as in Theorem 3.1, we see that the corresponding function $Z(l)$ is also positive solution of (E_1) and hence $Z \in (C_1^*)$ or (C_2^*) for $l \geq l_1 \geq l_0$.

First, assume that $Z \in (C_1^*)$: It follows from (E_1) that

$$(r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)')' \geq Q_1(l)Z^\beta(\sigma(l))$$

Integrating from $\rho(l)$ to l , we get

$$(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' \geq \frac{Z^\beta(\sigma(\rho(l)))}{r_2^*(l)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s Q_1(u) \, ds$$

Again integrating from $\rho(l)$ to l yields

$$Z'(l) \geq \frac{Z^{\beta/\alpha}(\mu(l))}{(r_1^*(l))^{1/\alpha}} \left(\int_{\rho(l)}^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s Q_1(u) \, du \, ds \right)^{1/\alpha}$$

Hence $Z(l)$ is a positive solution of the advanced differential inequality

$$Z'(l) - \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(l)} \int_{\rho(l)}^l \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s Q_1(u) \, du \, ds \right)^{1/\alpha} Z^{\beta/\alpha}(\mu(l)) \geq 0$$

But by Lemma 1 of [1], we conclude that the corresponding differential equation (3.21) also has a positive solution, which is a contradiction.

Next, assume that $Z \in (C_2^*)$: Integrating (E_1) from l to ∞ . We obtain

$$-r_2^*(l)(r_1^*(l)(Z'(l))^\alpha)' \geq \int_l^\infty Q_1(s)Z^\beta(\sigma(s))ds \geq Z^\beta(\sigma(l)) \int_l^\infty Q_1(s)ds$$

Divide the last inequality by $r_2^*(l)$ and then integrating from l to ∞ . one gets

$$\begin{aligned} Z'(l) &\geq \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(l)} \int_l^\infty \frac{Z^\beta(\sigma(s))}{r_2^*(s)} \int_s^\infty Q_1(u) \, du \, ds \right)^{1/\alpha} \\ &\geq \left(\frac{Z^\beta(\sigma(l))}{r_1^*(l)} \int_l^\infty \frac{1}{r_2^*(s)} \int_s^\infty Q_1(u) \, du \, ds \right)^{1/\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

consequently, $Z(l)$ is a positive solution of the advanced differential inequality

$$Z'(l) - \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(l)} \int_l^\infty \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_s^\infty Q_1(u) \, duds \right)^{1/\alpha} Z^{\beta/\alpha}(\sigma(l)) \geq 0$$

By Lemma 1 of [1], we deduce that there exists a positive solution of (3.22), which is again a contradiction. This ends the proof.

Remark 3.4. Note that from the proof of Theorem 3.3. that if

$$\int_{l_0}^{\infty} Q_1(l)dl = \infty \quad \text{or} \quad \int_{l_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_2^*(l)} \int_l^{\infty} Q_1(s)dsdl = \infty,$$

then a nonoscillatory solution $Z(l)$ of (E_1) cannot satisfy the case (C_2^*) .

Now, we present explicit criteria for the oscillation of all solutions of (E) for the different values of β and γ .

Corollary 3.5. Let (2.1) holds. Assume that there exist nondecreasing functions $\zeta(l), \delta(l), \omega(l) \in C^1([l_0, \infty), \mathbb{R})$ such that

$$\tau(l) < \zeta(l) < l, \quad l \geq l_0 \quad (3.23)$$

And

$$\sigma(l) > \delta(l) > \omega(l) > l, \quad l \geq l_0 \quad (3.24)$$

If $\beta = \gamma = \alpha$,

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_l^{\omega(l)} H_3(s)ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.25)$$

and

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\zeta(l)}^l G_2(s)ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.26)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. In view of well-known results in [21], we see that the equations (3.1), (3.2) are oscillatory under the conditions, (3.25) and (3.26) respectively. The conclusion now follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.6. Let conditions (3.23) and (3.24) holds and let $\beta = \alpha$ and $0 < \gamma < \alpha, \alpha \in (0,1)$. If condition (3.25) and

$$\int_{l_0}^{\infty} G_2(l)dl = \infty \quad (3.27)$$

holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. In view of well-known results in [21] and [12], we see that the equation (3.1) and (3.2) are oscillatory under the conditions (3.25) and (3.27) respectively. The conclusion now follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.7. Let conditions (3.23) and (3.24) holds and let $\beta > \alpha$ and $\gamma = \alpha$. If condition (3.26) and

$$\int_{l_1}^{\infty} H_3(l)dl = \infty \quad (3.28)$$

holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof . Proceeding as in Theorem 3.1, we arrive at (3.1). Since $\omega(l)$ is increasing and $\omega(l) > l$, we have from (3.1) that

$$\frac{\omega'(l)}{\omega^{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}}(l)} > H_3(l).$$

Integrating the last inequality from l_1 to ∞ , we obtain

$$\frac{\alpha}{(\beta - \alpha)\omega^{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}}(l_1)^{-1}} \geq \int_{l_1}^{\infty} H_3(s)ds$$

which contradicts (3.28). Therefore (3.1) is oscillatory and by condition (3.26), the equation (3.2) is oscillatory. Now, the conclusion follows from Theorem 3.1. This ends the proof.

Corollary 3.8. Let conditions (3.23) and (3.24) holds and let $\beta > \alpha$ and $0 < \gamma < \alpha, \alpha \in (0,1)$. If conditions (3.27) and (3.28) holds, then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. The proof follows from Corollary 3.6 and Corollary 3.7. This completes the proof.

Now, using Theorem 3.2, we get the following corollaries.

Corollary 3.9. Let (2.1) hold, $\gamma = \alpha$ and $\tau(l) \leq l$ for $l \geq l_1$. If

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\varsigma(l)}^l U_2(s) ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.29)$$

or

$$\limsup_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\varsigma(l)}^l U_2(s) ds > 1 \quad (3.30)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Corollary 3.10. Let (2.1) hold, $\gamma > \alpha$ and $\tau(l) \leq l$ for $l \geq l_1$. If

$$\limsup_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\varsigma(l)}^l U_2(s) ds > 1 \quad (3.31)$$

then equation is oscillatory.

Next, by using Theorem 3.3 instead of Theorem 3.1, we get the following corollaries.

Corollary 3.11. Let condition (2.1) and (3.20) holds and let $\beta > \alpha$. If

$$\int_{l_0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(s)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s \frac{1}{r_2^*(s_1)} \int_{\rho(s_1)}^{s_1} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 \right)^{1/\alpha} ds = \infty \quad (3.32)$$

and

$$\int_{l_0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(s)} \int_s^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_2^*(s_1)} \int_{s_1}^{\infty} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 \right)^{1/\alpha} ds = \infty \quad (3.33)$$

then equation (E) is oscillatory.

Proof. The proof follows from Corollary 3.7 and this ends the proof.

Corollary 3.12. Let conditions (2.1) and (3.20) holds and let $\beta = \alpha$. If

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{l_0}^{\mu(l)} \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(s)} \int_{\rho(s)}^s \frac{1}{r_2^*(s_1)} \int_{\rho(s_1)}^{s_1} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 \right)^{1/\alpha} ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.34)$$

and

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_l^{\rho(l)} \left(\frac{1}{r_1^*(s)} \int_s^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_2^*(s_1)} \int_{s_1}^{\infty} Q_1(s_2) ds_2 ds_1 \right)^{1/\alpha} ds > \frac{1}{e} \quad (3.35)$$

Proof. In view of well-known results in [21], we see that the equation (3.21) and (3.22) are oscillatory under the conditions (3.32) and (3.33) respectively. Now the conclusion follows from Theorem 3.3. This ends the proof.

4. EXAMPLES

In this section, we present some examples to validate the main results.

Example 4.1. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$(l^2((Z'(l))^3)')' = aZ^3\left(\frac{3l}{2}\right) + bZ\left(\frac{l}{2}\right), l \geq 1 \quad (4.1)$$

Where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. Simple calculations show that $\mathcal{A}_2(l) = \frac{1}{l}$ and condition (2.1) holds. Next, $r_1^*(l) = l, r_2^*(l) = 1, Q_1(l) = \frac{a}{l}$ and $Q_2(l) = \frac{b}{l}$.

The transformed equation is

$$(l(Z'(l))^3)'' = \frac{a}{l}Z^3\left(\frac{3l}{2}\right) + \frac{b}{l}Z\left(\frac{l}{2}\right), \quad l \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form.

Choose $\delta(l) = \frac{5l}{4}, \omega(l) = \frac{9l}{8}$, so that condition (3.24) holds. Next, choose $\zeta(l) = \frac{3l}{4}$ so that condition (3.23) holds.

With further calculation, we see that

$$H_3(l) = \frac{a}{8}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 \left[\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{2/3}\right]^3 l^2 \quad \text{and} \quad G_2(l) = \frac{3b}{8}[1 - l^{-2/3}].$$

The conditions (3.25) becomes

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_l^{\frac{9l}{8}} \frac{a}{8}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 \left[\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 - \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{2/3}\right]^3 s^2 ds = \infty > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.25) holds for all $a > 0$. Next, the condition (3.27) becomes

$$\int_1^{\infty} \frac{3b}{8}[1 - s^{-2/3}] ds = \infty,$$

that is, condition (3.27) holds for all $b > 0$. By Corollary 3.6, the equation (4.1) is oscillatory for all $a > 0, b > 0$.

Example 4.2. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$(l^2((Z'(l))^{1/3})')' = aZ^3(2l) + bZ^{1/3}\left(\frac{l}{2}\right), l \geq 1 \quad (4.2)$$

where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. Simple calculations show that $\mathcal{A}_2(l) = \frac{1}{l}$ and condition (2.1) holds. Next, $r_1^*(l) = l, r_2^*(l) = 1, Q_1(l) = \frac{a}{l}$ and $Q_2(l) = \frac{b}{l}$.

The transformed equation is

$$(l(Z'(l))^{1/3})'' = \frac{a}{l}Z^3(2l) + \frac{b}{l}Z^{1/3}\left(\frac{l}{2}\right), \quad l \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form.

Choose $\delta(l) = \frac{3l}{2}, \omega(l) = \frac{5l}{4}$, so that condition (3.24) holds. Next, choose $\zeta(l) = \frac{3l}{4}$ so that condition (3.23) holds.

With further calculation, we see that

$$H_3(l) = a\left(\frac{7}{72}\right)^3 \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^9 l^2 \quad \text{and} \quad G_2(l) = \frac{b}{8}[1 - l^{-2}].$$

The conditions (3.28) becomes

$$\int_1^{\infty} a\left(\frac{7}{72}\right)^3 \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^9 s^2 ds = \infty,$$

that is, condition (3.28) holds for all $a > 0$. Next, the condition (3.26) becomes

$$\liminf_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{3l}{4}}^l \frac{b}{8}[1 - l^{-2}] ds = \infty > \frac{1}{e},$$

that is, condition (3.26) holds for all $b > 0$. By Corollary 3.7, the equation (4.2) is oscillatory for all $a > 0, b > 0$.

Example 4.3. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$\left(l^2 \left(\frac{1}{l^2} Z'(l) \right)' \right)' = a l Z^3 \left(\frac{3l}{2} \right) + b l Z^{1/3} \left(\frac{l}{2} \right), l \geq 1 \quad (4.3)$$

Where $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ are constants. Simple calculations show that $\mathcal{A}_2(l) = \frac{1}{l}$ and condition (2.1) holds. Next, $r_1^*(l) = \frac{1}{l}, r_2^*(l) = 1, Q_1(l) = a$ and $Q_2(l) = b$.

The transformed equation is

$$\left(\frac{1}{l} Z'(l) \right)'' = a Z^3 \left(\frac{3l}{2} \right) + b Z^{1/3} \left(\frac{l}{2} \right), \quad l \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form.

Choose $\delta(l) = \frac{5l}{4}, \omega(l) = \frac{9l}{8}$, so that condition (3.24) holds. Next, choose $\zeta(l) = \frac{3l}{4}$ so that condition (3.23) holds.

With further calculation, we see that

$$H_3(l) = a \left(\frac{11}{256} \right)^3 l^9 \text{ and } G_2(l) = \frac{b}{4^{1/3}} \log(l/2) l^{1/3}.$$

The conditions (3.27) becomes

$$\int_1^{\infty} a \left(\frac{11}{256} \right)^3 s^9 ds = \infty,$$

that is, condition (3.27) holds for all $a > 0$. Next, the condition (3.28) becomes

$$\int_1^{\infty} \frac{b}{4^{1/3}} \log(s/2) s^{1/3} ds = \infty,$$

that is, condition (3.28) holds for all $b > 0$. By Corollary 3.8, the equation (4.3) is oscillatory for all $a > 0, b > 0$.

Example 4.4. Consider the third-order semi-canonical functional differential equation

$$\left(l^2 \left(\frac{1}{l} Z'(l) \right)' \right)' = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{l}} Z^3 \left(\frac{3l}{2} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{l}} Z^3 \left(\frac{l}{2} \right), l \geq 1 \quad (4.4)$$

Simple calculations show that $\mathcal{A}_2(l) = \frac{1}{l}$ and condition (2.1) holds. Next, $r_1^*(l) = r_2^*(l) = 1, Q_1(l) = \frac{\lambda}{l^{3/2}}$ and $Q_2(l) = \frac{\lambda}{l^{3/2}}$. The transformed equation is

$$Z'''(l) = \frac{\lambda}{l^{3/2}} Z^3 \left(\frac{3l}{2} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{l^{3/2}} Z^3 \left(\frac{l}{2} \right), \quad l \geq 1,$$

which is in canonical form.

Choose $\zeta(l) = \frac{4l}{5}$ so that condition (3.23) holds. With further calculation, we see that

$$U_2(l) = 2\lambda \left(\frac{3}{10} \right)^3 \left[1 - \frac{1}{l^{1/2}} \right].$$

The conditions (3.31) becomes

$$\limsup_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\frac{4l}{5}}^l U_2(s) ds = \limsup_{l \rightarrow \infty} 2\lambda \left(\frac{3}{10} \right)^3 [l - 2l^{1/2}] = \infty,$$

that is, condition (3.31) holds for all $a > 0$. By Corollary 3.10, the equation (4.4) is oscillatory for all $a > 0, b > 0$.

5.CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have established oscillation criteria of semi-canonical quasi-linear differential equation (E) with mixed arguments into the canonical form. We examine the oscillatory behavior of (E) in a easy way, by comparing the third order semi-canonical differential equation to that of first order delay or advanced type equations. Further, to validate the oscillatory behavior of the equation, examples where given. Hence the results obtained are new and a further contribution to the oscillation theory of functional differential equations with mixed arguments.

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